

Article

Population-Based Registry Analysis of Antidiabetics Dispensations: Trend Use in Spain between 2015 and 2018 with Reference to Driving

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Abstract: Insulins and some oral antidiabetics are considered to be driving-impairing medicines (DIM) and they belong to the Driving under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol, and medicines (DRUID) category I (minor influence on fitness to drive). The trend of antidiabetics use in Castilla y León from 2015 to 2018 is presented through a population-based registry study. Treatment duration with these medicines and the concomitant use of other DIMs were observed. An adjustment method was used with information from the drivers' license census. For all calculations, age and gender were taken into account. 3.98% of the general population used at least one antidiabetic, as well as 2.92% of drivers. The consumption of antidiabetics in men was higher than in women (4.35% vs. 3.61%, $p = 0.001$), and the use increases with age, especially from 35–39 years to 75–79 years in men and 85–89 years in women. Antidiabetics were consumed chronically, specifically 100% in the case of insulins and 95% in the case of oral antidiabetics. In addition to antidiabetics, 2.5 ± 1.86 DIMs were consumed, mainly anxiolytics (25.53%), opioids (23.03%), other analgesics and antipiretics (19.13%), and antidepressants (17.73%). Collaboration between pharmacists and physicians is a priority to clearly transmitting risks to patients. It is necessary that the health authorities include information on DIMs, such as the DRUID classification, in the prescription and dispensing software.

Keywords: antidiabetics; diabetes mellitus; insulins; driving impairing medicines; driving under the influence

1. Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is one of the most prevalent chronic disease worldwide [1], affecting more than 400 million people [2]. In 2019, in Spain, DM affected one in ten adults between 20 and 79 years of age, reaching a prevalence of 10.5%, which is considered to be slightly elevated as compared to the average in European countries (8.9%) [3].

Diabetes can affect fitness to drive [1,4–6]. Chronic complications, such as retinopathy or peripheral neuropathy, can impair sensory or motor function [6,7]. On the other hand, acute complications, such as hypoglycemia or hyperglycemia, can affect perception, motor skills, cognition, and judgment, and may cause loss of consciousness during driving [7,8], which may result in road crashes [9–11].

Indeed, hypoglycemia is one of the main adverse effects of insulin therapy [10,12,13], as well as of oral antidiabetics, especially sulfonylureas and meglitinides, [12,14]. Notwithstanding, the results from studies on driving impairment in patients with DM may be contradictory, even in the face of the existing evidence on hypoglycemia [15], leading to the current restrictions for these patients to drive, as established in Europe and the USA [4,8,16].

Study Aim

In Spain, since 2000, DM prevalence has increased, and, thus, the use of insulins (57.5%) and oral antidiabetics (52.5%), which, overall, is 13% higher than in 2000 [17], with a predominance of users of oral antidiabetics [18].

The risks for driving associated with insulin and many oral antidiabetics is well recognized into the Driving Under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol and medicines (DRUID) classification (Supplementary Table S1), which group these medicines in the category I (i.e., minor influence on fitness to drive) [19], mainly due to the likelihood of hypoglycemia occurrence during treatment. However, although there are studies on antidiabetic use at national and European level, to our knowledge, no data on the use of these medicines in the driver population are available.

This study presents findings on consumption of insulins and oral antidiabetics in a European population. Data on dispensation at pharmacies of these medicines in the largest region of Spain for the years 2015 to 2018 were assessed. Our analysis also considers the duration of treatment and concomitant use of these medicines with other driving impairing medicines (DIM), and the distribution by age and gender of users. Finally, as previously performed in other studies by our team, an adjustment method has been carried out in order to estimate the real consumption of these medicines in the driver population [20–24].

2. Results

From 2015 to 2018, five millions of packages of antidiabetics were dispensed to the population (Supplementary Table S2), mostly oral antidiabetics (71.47%) than insulins (28.53%). These findings show that the real proportion of consumers into the general population was 3.98%, 3.13% under an oral antidiabetic, 1.56% under insulin, and 0.71% under both an oral antidiabetic and an insulin. Men were most commonly under treatment with antidiabetics than women (4.35% vs. 3.61%, $X^2 = 18831.883$, $p = 0.001$; Table 1). As expected, 100% of insulins and more than 95% of oral antidiabetics was of chronic use (Table 1). The consumption of all antidiabetics (Figure 1) and separately insulins and oral antidiabetics increase with age (Figure 2), especially from 35–39 years to 75–79 years in men and to 85–89 years in women.

Sitagliptin in combination with metformin (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) code A10BD07) and vildagliptin in combination with metformin (ATC code A10BD08), were the most consumed oral antidiabetics (more than 335,000 packages per year). Insulin glargine (ATC code A10AE04) and insulin aspart, intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting (ATC code A10AD05) was the most consumed insulins (more than 180,000 packages per year). Detailed oral antidiabetics and insulins dispensation are presented online (Supplementary Table S3).

Yearly users of antidiabetics also took 2.50 ± 1.86 DIMs (Table 1), with higher values in women than in men (2.76 vs. 2.19, $t = -74.63$, $p = 0.001$), and represented by anxiolytics (25.53%), opioids (23.03%), other analgesics and antipyretics (19.13%), and antidepressants (17.73%). In addition, chronic use and yearly use of these medicines increased, respectively, by 32.02% ($Z = 47.25$, $p < 0.0001$, 3.31% in 2015 vs. 4.37% in 2018) and 31.55% ($Z = 36.24$, $p < 0.0001$, 3.36% in 2015 vs. 4.42% in 2018; Table 2; Figure 3).

Table 1. Consumption of antidiabetics according to CONCYLIA database and the Castile and León drivers' license census data.

Gender	Population Using Antidiabetics % (95CI)			Drivers Using Antidiabetics % (95CI)		
	Total	Insulins	Oral Antidiabetics	Total	Insulins	Oral Antidiabetics
Total	3.98 (3.95–4)	1.56 (1.54–1.58)	3.13 (3.1–3.15)	2.92 (2.89–2.94)	1.15 (1.13–1.16)	2.44 (2.42–2.47)
Male	4.35 (4.32–4.39)	1.64 (1.61–1.66)	3.48 (3.44–3.51)	4.22 (4.17–4.26)	1.58 (1.55–1.61)	3.62 (3.58–3.66)
Female	3.61 (3.58–3.65)	1.49 (1.47–1.51)	2.79 (2.76–2.82)	0.98 (0.96–1.01)	0.5 (0.49–0.52)	0.7 (0.68–0.73)
	$X^2 = 18,831.883; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 7157.779; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 14,785.013; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 17,826.133; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 8420.777; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 9520.731; p = 0.001$
Chronic use						
Total	3.93 (3.9–3.95)	1.56 (1.54–1.58)	3.06 (3.04–3.09)	2.88 (2.85–2.91)	1.15 (1.13–1.16)	2.23 (2.21–2.26)
Male	4.3 (4.27–4.34)	1.63 (1.61–1.66)	3.41 (3.38–3.45)	4.17 (4.12–4.21)	1.58 (1.55–1.6)	3.32 (3.28–3.35)
Female	3.57 (3.53–3.6)	1.49 (1.47–1.51)	2.73 (2.7–2.76)	0.97 (0.94–0.99)	0.5 (0.48–0.52)	0.61 (0.59–0.63)
	$X^2 = 18,734.605; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 7158.431; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 14,639.994; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 17,630.868; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 8420.042; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 9172.203; p = 0.001$
Average of driving impairing medicines. Population antidiabetics use						
Total	2.5 ± 1.86	2.63 ± 1.95	2.48 ± 1.84	2.25 ± 1.77	2.38 ± 1.88	2.22 ± 1.73
Male	2.19 ± 1.68	2.33 ± 1.79	2.16 ± 1.65	2.17 ± 1.7	2.31 ± 1.81	2.13 ± 1.65
Female	2.76 ± 1.96	2.87 ± 2.04	2.75 ± 1.95	2.68 ± 2.07	2.68 ± 2.11	2.74 ± 2.06
	$t = -74.63; p = 0.001$	$t = -42.45; p = 0.001$	$t = -69.96; p = 0.001$	$t = -27.53; p = 0.001$	$t = -13.22; p = 0.001$	$t = -27.94; p = 0.001$

Abbreviations: 95CI, confidence interval. X^2 , t : Chi squared and T -Student test for comparison between men and women.

Figure 1. Frequency of antidiabetics use by the general population and the driver population.

Figure 2. Frequency of use by the type of antidiabetic.

Table 2. Evolution of antidiabetics use in Castile and León (2015–2018).

Gender	Population Using Antidiabetics % (95CI)				Drivers Using Antidiabetics % (95CI)			
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2015	2016	2017	2018
Total	3.36 (3.33–3.38)	4.11 (4.09–4.14)	4.02 (3.99–4.04)	4.42 (4.39–4.45)	2.36 (2.34–2.39)	3.02 (2.99–3.05)	3.01 (2.98–3.04)	3.28 (3.25–3.31)
Male	3.63 (3.6–3.67)	4.46 (4.42–4.5)	4.42 (4.39–4.46)	4.9 (4.86–4.94)	3.43 (3.39–3.47)	4.34 (4.3–4.38)	4.35 (4.3–4.39)	4.75 (4.7–4.79)
Female	3.09 (3.06–3.12)	3.78 (3.74–3.81)	3.63 (3.6–3.66)	3.95 (3.92–3.99)	0.74 (0.72–0.76)	1.04 (1.01–1.06)	1.03 (1–1.05)	1.12 (1.1–1.15)
	$X^2 = 4070.524; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4863.585; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4741.491; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 5184.767; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4160.909; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4389.486; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4570.11; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4805.053; p = 0.001$
Type of antidiabetic								
Insulins								
Total	1.31 (1.29–1.32)	1.65 (1.64–1.67)	1.57 (1.55–1.58)	1.72 (1.7–1.74)	0.95 (0.94–0.97)	1.21 (1.19–1.23)	1.17 (1.15–1.18)	1.26 (1.24–1.28)
Male	1.36 (1.34–1.38)	1.72 (1.69–1.74)	1.65 (1.62–1.67)	1.82 (1.79–1.84)	1.3 (1.28–1.33)	1.66 (1.64–1.69)	1.61 (1.58–1.63)	1.74 (1.71–1.77)
Female	1.26 (1.24–1.28)	1.59 (1.57–1.61)	1.49 (1.46–1.51)	1.62 (1.6–1.64)	0.42 (0.41–0.44)	0.52 (0.51–0.54)	0.51 (0.49–0.53)	0.56 (0.54–0.58)
	$X^2 = 1518.236; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 1988.255; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 1785.798; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 1898.464; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 1911.783; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2146.022; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2202.878; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2200.603; p = 0.001$
Oral antidiabetic								
Total	2.59 (2.57–2.61)	3.19 (3.16–3.21)	3.19 (3.16–3.21)	3.55 (3.52–3.57)	1.78 (1.76–1.8)	2.33 (2.31–2.36)	2.38 (2.35–2.4)	2.62 (2.59–2.65)
Male	2.84 (2.81–2.87)	3.51 (3.48–3.54)	3.56 (3.53–3.6)	4 (3.97–4.04)	2.67 (2.63–2.7)	3.43 (3.4–3.47)	3.52 (3.48–3.56)	3.9 (3.85–3.94)
Female	2.34 (2.32–2.37)	2.87 (2.84–2.9)	2.82 (2.8–2.85)	3.11 (3.08–3.14)	0.42 (0.41–0.44)	0.68 (0.66–0.7)	0.68 (0.66–0.7)	0.75 (0.73–0.77)
	$X^2 = 3198.26; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 3687.492; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 3749.531; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 4167.533; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 1910.429; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2355.727; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2541.26; p = 0.001$	$X^2 = 2723.007; p = 0.001$
Average of driving impairing medicines; Population antidiabetics use								
Total	2.5 ± 1.88	2.53 ± 1.89	2.47 ± 1.84	2.51 ± 1.83	2.22 ± 1.75	2.28 ± 1.81	2.23 ± 1.75	2.28 ± 1.76
Male	2.16 ± 1.66	2.23 ± 1.73	2.16 ± 1.66	2.22 ± 1.68	2.14 ± 1.68	2.2 ± 1.74	2.14 ± 1.67	2.2 ± 1.69
Female	2.77 ± 1.99	2.78 ± 1.98	2.73 ± 1.94	2.75 ± 1.92	2.69 ± 2.09	2.68 ± 2.09	2.67 ± 2.08	2.69 ± 2.02
	$t = -37.42; p = 0.001$	$t = -36.63; p = 0.001$	$t = -37.99; p = 0.001$	$t = -37.53; p = 0.001$	$t = -12.4; p = 0.001$	$t = -13.15; p = 0.001$	$t = -14.61; p = 0.001$	$t = -14.77; p = 0.001$

Abbreviations: 95CI; confidence interval. X^2 , t : Chi squared and T -Student test for comparison between men and women.

Figure 3. Evolution of antidiabetics use in Castilla y León (2015–2018).

With respect to drivers (Supplementary Table S2), 2.92% used at least one antidiabetic, 0.51% taking both an oral antidiabetic and an insulin, being men users four times more frequent than women users (4.22% vs. 0.98%, $X^2 = 17,826.133$, $p = 0.001$; Table 1) and, as in the general population, in 100% of cases these medicines were used chronically. The consumption increased with age, but, among women drivers, the peak of use of antidiabetics is achieved 20 years earlier than in women into the general population (Figures 1 and 2). Finally, chronic and yearly use of antidiabetics increased by 40% ($Z = 70.69$, $p < 0.0001$, 2.36% in 2015 vs. 3.28% in 2018; Table 2; Figure 3), and the concomitant use of other DIMs was similar to that observed into the general population, with a use of more DIM among women drivers.

3. Discussion

According to our results, between 2015 and 2018, almost 4% out of the population and 3% of drivers in Castile and León were under treatment with oral antidiabetics alone or in combination with insulins, and mostly men consumed more antidiabetics than women, both into the general population and among drivers. The chronic use of fixed combinations of oral antidiabetics and insulins were noted,

and users took these medicines with more than two driving-impairing medicines, mostly anxiolytics and analgesics, including opioids.

Our findings confirm the increase in the use of antidiabetics claimed by public national data [18], which is consistent with the increase in the global prevalence of DM [3] and with aging of the population, which is particularly relevant in Spain. In the other hand, as compared to other European OECD countries, in Spain the oral antidiabetics and insulin consumption is 14% higher [17]. In this sense, the increase in consumption per age of antidiabetics is also consistent with age distribution of DM, with a lower prevalence in young adults when compared with those more aged [3]. Furthermore, higher use among men is consistent with higher disease prevalence in male sex individuals [3], and higher concomitant use of other driving-impairing medicines is observed among women into both the general population and the driver population (e.g., anxiolytics, opioids, and antidepressants) [21,23,24].

All over the world, the majority of diabetic people have type 2 diabetes (90–95%), which explains the observed greater consumption of oral antidiabetics when compared to insulins [25]. Our results also show that two dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors (DPP4) considered as second-line treatments were used more frequently, in combination with metformin, probably to induce a greater weight reduction without intense hypoglycemia [26,27]. Moreover, intermediate or long acting insulin preparations were preferred, as expected according to available evidence [28].

Surprisingly, metformin alone that does not include the pictogram “medicines and driving”, which is, not considered a driving-impairing medicine, was the most consumed antidiabetic medicine, with an average of around 715,000 packages per year. According to our findings, metformin was used, on average, by more than 3% of the population each year (45% of the global consumption of oral antidiabetics) [18], which is in line with current recommendations. Nevertheless, hypoglycemia is a patent risk for all antidiabetics. Prudence and common sense is thus recommended to clinicians when prescribing this and other oral antidiabetics that do not include the pictogram “medicines and driving” (Supplementary Table S4).

Importantly, the evidence on DM and driving is sometimes conflictive. Koepsell et al. [29] and Cox et al. [30] show an increase in the risk for motor vehicle crashes of around 30% as compared to non-diabetic drivers. However, the Emergency Care Research Institute (ECRI) found an increase in such risk of around 12–19% [31]. It seems that the real risk for car crashes is uncertain or slightly increased: rate ratios in insulin-treated diabetics of 0.54 to 1.8 [25], and standardized incidence ratios in oral antidiabetics-treated and insulin-treated diabetics of 1.2 to 1.4 [5] are found. Indeed, separately, oral antidiabetics and insulins should be associated to a lower risk [10] or no risk [13,32], which suggests that really an adequate monitoring of blood glucose levels of patients, to avoid hypoglycemia is of crucial importance [6]. Therefore, antidiabetics should be prescribed and consumed appropriately, even those not including the “medicines and driving” pictogram. In this sense, susceptible populations, such as chronic kidney disease patients and other individuals affected by chronic and potentially impairing diseases, should be at the focus of personalized strategies to avoid hypoglycemia [33].

In Europe and in the USA, diabetics are restricted for obtaining driver’s licenses [4,8,16,34]. Once more, it is of great importance that healthcare professionals aware of risks for a safe driving in this patient population, in order to provide adequate information to these patients [35], for advising them on risk reduction [30]: an important proportion of healthcare professionals do not know hypoglycemia and its relation for a safe driving [36].

In addition to clinicians, pharmacists take responsibility for educating patients on potential risks for driving through drug counseling [37]. In a study on the implementation of dispensing support tools, it was observed that the inclusion of details on DRUID category of drugs dispensed in the software of daily use had a positive effect in risk communication to patients [38].

Finally, this study has some limitations that should be mentioned. Information on consumption of oral antidiabetics and insulins in hospitals or from the private practice has not been taken into account. Nevertheless, this was not an important impediment, as a high percentage of the population are included in our public health insurance system. Similarly, in the CONCYLIA database there is no

information on dispensing “over the counter” medications, but all antidiabetics have a mandatory medical prescription. Lastly, it has been necessary to use an extrapolation method to estimate dispensation of antidiabetics to drivers. For this, weighting was performed to adjust the consumption of antidiabetics among licensed drivers by age and gender, as had made in a previous studies [20–24]. However, the results do not represent an authentic stratification of use, because the CONCYLIA database does not record information on driving.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Real-World Study Details

The results from an epidemiological population-based registry study are presented here in accordance to the REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected Data (RECORD) recommendations, in order to adequately provide real-world evidence into the topic addressed [39]. The years 2015 to 2018 data on dispensations at pharmacies of insulins (ATC subgroups A10AB and A10AC) and many oral antidiabetics (ATC subgroups A10BA, A10BB, A10BD, A10BF, A10BG, A10BH, A10BJ, A10BK, and A10BX), which are considered DIM (Supplementary Table S1) were assessed. Since 2011, in our country all DIMs include the “medicines and driving” pictogram on the packaging, with the aim of improving knowledge about the effects of these medicines on driving ability [20], and such pictogram was the way to identify antidiabetics for entering to calculations.

Our pharmaceutical care information system, CONCYLIA (<http://www.saludcastillayleon.es/portalmedicamento/es/indicadores-informes/concylia>), contains data on the dispensation of all medicines covered by our public health insurance system at pharmacies in Castile and Leon, such as including DIMs. This population registry does not contain information on medicines dispensed at hospitals, into the private practice, and those considered as ‘over the counter’ medications; however, the Spanish national health insurance system cover more than 95% of the population and antidiabetics are only on prescription. There is no recorded information about driving in the CONCYLIA database, so as in other studies carried out by our team [20–24], weighting was performed to obtain the adjusted antidiabetics consumption for licensed drivers according to age and gender while using the Castile and León drivers’ license census data (<http://www.dgt.es/es/seguridad-vial/estadisticas-e-indicadores/permisos-conduccion/>). Dispensation was considered to be equivalent to consumption, since the adherence rate in Castile and León patients is high. This study was approved by our local ethics committee on 17 March 2016 (reference number PI 16-387).

The following variables were considered: (1) frequency of consumption of antidiabetics, (2) chronic use (≥ 30 days) and yearly use of antidiabetics, and (3) concomitant use of antidiabetics with other DIMs.

4.2. Statistical Analysis

In all analyses, the distribution of the population by age and gender has been taken into account (Supplementary Table S2). Frequencies (percentages) with their corresponding 95% confidence interval (95% CI) or as means accompanied by their standard deviations (SD) have been calculated. Differences between continuous variables were calculated while using Student’s *t*-Test (*t*), and those between categorical variables using Pearson’s Chi-squared test (X^2). The Cochran–Armitage trend test was used to evaluate the trends of consumption by years (*Z*). The level of significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. All statistical analyzes were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 24.0; SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, USA). Finally, Microsoft Word and Excel (Microsoft Office version 365; Microsoft, Redmon, WA, USA) were used for preparing this manuscript.

5. Conclusions

A significant increase in the consumption of oral antidiabetics and insulins has been observed between 2015 and 2018, with a specific pattern of use into the general population and among drivers,

and with a concomitant use of other driving-impairing medicines. Despite the fact that the medicines addressed belong to the DRUID category I (minor influence on fitness to drive), the use of antidiabetics not considered as DIM should be taken into account when evaluating risks issues.

The prevention of hypoglycemia is of crucial importance, so that monitoring of patients with DM should be performed [40]. In this sense, healthcare professionals should educate patients with DM on symptoms and the predisposing conditions for this acute complication [14], and promoting adequate control of blood glucose [6]. Evidently, clinicians must particularly be sufficiently prepared and able to decide which people with DM have an unacceptable driving risk and must be excluded from driving [10]. However, in our opinion, health professionals are required to transmit clear and precise information regarding the meaning of the “medicines and driving” pictogram. A Spanish study revealed that only 15.9% of the population knew of the existence of the pictogram and the majority said that they had received no adequate information from the different healthcare professionals concerning the effects of the medicaments on driving abilities [41].

DIMs consumption can be considered a road safety problem, while taking into account that, according to the WHO Global Status Report On Road Safety, traffic collisions cause 1.3 million deaths every year [42], and in Spain at least 34% of the population consumes these medications [20]. Finally, it is necessary to strengthen collaboration between pharmacists and physicians in order to improve the communication of risks to the patient [38], and healthcare authorities should promote the inclusion of additional tools in prescription and dispensing tools.

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8247/13/8/165/s1>, Table S1: Antidiabetics available in Castilla León (2015–2018), Table S2: Evolution of the Castilla y León population and drivers’s licences (2015–2018), Table S3: List of the 20 antidiabetics with pictogram “medicines and driving” more consumed in Castilla y León into the study period (Packages/year), Table S4: Oral antidiabetic without pictogram “medicines and driving” consumption in Castilla y León into the study period (Packages/year).

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Table S1. Oral antidiabetics and insulins available in Castile and León (2015–2018).

Type of antidiabetic	Code ATC	Name	Pictogram	DRUID category
Insulins	A10AB01	Insulin (human), fast acting	√	I
	A10AB04	Insulin lispro, fast acting	√	I
	A10AB05	Insulin aspart, fast acting	√	I
	A10AB06	Insulin glulisine	√	I
	A10AC01	Insulin (human), intermediate acting	√	I
	A10AC04	Insulin lispro, intermediate acting	√	I
	A10AD01	Insulin (human), intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting	√	I
	A10AD04	Insulin lispro, intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting	√	I
	A10AD05	Insulin aspart, intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting	√	I
	A10AE04	Insuline glargine	√	I
	A10AE05	Insulin detemir	√	I
A10AE06	Insulin degludec (available from 2016)	√	I	
Oral antidiabetics	A10BA02	Metformin	X	0
	A10BB01	Glibenclamide	√	I
	A10BB07	Glipizide	√	I
	A10BB09	Glicazide	√	I
	A10BB12	Glimepiride	√	I
	A10BB91	Glisentide	√	I
	A10BD05	Metformin and pioglitazone	X	0
	A10BD06	Glimepiride and pioglitazone	√	I
	A10BD07	Metformin and sitagliptin	√	I
	A10BD08	Metformin and vildagliptin	√	I
	A10BD09	Pioglitazone and alogliptin	√	I
	A10BD10	Metformine and saxagliptin	√	I
	A10BD11	Metformin and linagliptin	√	I
	A10BD13	Metformin and alogliptin	√	I
	A10BD15	Metformin and dapagliflozin	√	I
	A10BD16	Metformin and canagliflozin	√	I
	A10BD19	Linagliptin and empagliflozin (available from 2018)	√	I
	A10BD20	Metformin and empagliflozin (available from 2016)	√	I
	A10BF01	Acarbose	X	0
	A10BF02	Miglitol	X	0
	A10BG03	Pioglitazone	X	0
	A10BH01	Sitagliptin	√	I
	A10BH02	Vildagliptin	√	I
	A10BH03	Saxagliptin	√	I
	A10BH04	Alogliptin	√	I
	A10BH05	Linagliptin	√	I
	A10BJ01	Exenatide	√	I
	A10BJ02	Liraglutide	√	I
	A10BJ03	Lixisenatide	√	I
	A10BJ04	Albiglutide	√	I
	A10BJ05	Dulaglutide	√	I
	A10BK01	Dapagliflozin	√	I
	A10BK02	Canagliflozin	√	I
A10BK03	Empagliflozin	√	I	
A10BX01	Guar gum	X	0	
A10BX02	Repaglinide	√	I	
A10BX03	Nateglinide	√	I	

ATC, DRUID, DRiving Under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol, and medicines.

Table S2. Evolution of the Castile and León population and drivers's licences (2015–2018).

Rank age	Population											
	2015			2016			2017			2018		
	Men	Women	Total									
0-4	45 405	42 504	87 909	44 382	41 386	85 768	42 905	40 144	83 049	41 604	39 121	80 725
5-9	50 925	48 078	99 003	50 665	47 821	98 486	50 035	47 344	97 379	48 594	45 657	94 251
10-14	49 439	47 220	96 659	49 847	47 730	97 577	50 316	48 259	98 575	51 124	48 407	99 531
15-19	48 620	46 904	95 524	48 862	46 935	95 797	48 939	46 706	95 645	49 610	47 885	97 495
20-24	54 724	53 382	108 106	53 230	52 333	105 563	52 182	51 246	103 428	51 428	50 777	102 205
25-29	62 787	61 247	124 034	61 109	59 382	120 491	59 522	57 531	117 053	58 298	56 506	114 804
30-34	75 089	71 664	146 753	71 742	68 841	140 583	68 575	66 051	134 626	65 942	63 241	129 183
35-39	90 372	87 031	177 403	87 267	83 676	170 943	83 600	80 400	164 000	79 663	76 944	156 607
40-44	92 686	89 879	182 565	92 967	90 094	183 061	92 799	89 681	182 480	92 434	89 499	181 933
45-49	93 082	91 643	184 725	93 035	91 392	184 427	92 076	90 588	182 664	91 744	89 952	181 696
50-54	93 252	90 618	183 870	93 251	91 395	184 646	93 500	91 893	185 393	92 913	92 426	185 339
55-59	87 280	84 212	171 492	88 988	85 894	174 882	89 831	86 956	176 787	90 852	87 988	178 840
60-64	72 448	69 337	141 785	75 073	72 029	147 102	77 520	74 875	152 395	79 640	77 583	157 223
65-69	65 430	66 777	132 207	66 403	67 268	133 671	67 615	68 053	135 668	67 660	67 825	135 485
70-74	56 526	61 968	118 494	58 076	63 396	121 472	58 913	64 067	122 980	60 320	64 908	125 228
75-79	45 154	56 939	102 093	43 540	53 807	97 347	43 510	52 990	96 500	46 205	55 251	101 456
80-84	44 543	62 354	106 897	44 319	62 772	107 091	42 312	60 175	102 487	39 465	56 065	95 530
85-89	27 547	46 335	73 882	28 618	47 555	76 173	29 407	48 337	77 744	29 731	48 690	78 421
≥ 90	13 282	30 034	43 316	14 119	31 809	45 928	14 662	32 970	47 632	15 333	34 407	49 740
Total	1 168 591	1 208 126	2 376 717	1 165 493	1 205 515	2 371 008	1 158 219	1 198 266	2 356 485	1 152 560	1 193 132	2 345 692

Rank age	Licensed drivers											
	2015			2016			2017			2018		
	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total
15-19	9 282	5 586	14 868	9 238	5 634	14 872	8 357	4 689	13 046	8 702	5 102	13 804
20-24	43 294	35 387	78 681	42 165	34 280	76 445	40 859	33 207	74 066	39 837	32 570	72 407
25-29	55 831	50 618	106 449	53 617	48 755	102 372	51 913	46 861	98 774	50 269	45 329	95 598
30-34	69 810	61 387	131 197	66 192	58 489	124 681	62 677	56 134	118 811	59 765	53 560	113 325
35-39	86 841	75 838	162 679	83 112	72 880	155 992	79 204	70 129	149 333	74 693	66 771	141 464

40-44	89 294	76 277	165 571	88 673	76 856	165 529	88 025	76 717	164 742	87 163	76 513	163 676
45-49	90 151	74 310	164 461	89 641	74 389	164 030	88 611	74 242	162 853	87 961	74 534	162 495
50-54	90 450	67 282	157 732	90 290	69 036	159 326	90 158	70 695	160 853	89 420	72 062	161 482
55-59	85 820	56 346	142 166	87 607	59 781	147 388	88 543	62 443	150 986	89 826	64 796	154 622
60-64	71 450	36 255	107 705	74 219	40 173	114 392	76 748	44 338	121 086	79 194	48 281	127 475
65-69	62 572	23 964	86 536	63 824	26 068	89 892	65 577	28 466	94 043	65 978	30 748	96 726
70-74	51 161	12 390	63 551	52 595	13 755	66 350	53 663	15 096	68 759	55 094	16 442	71 536
75-79	35 993	5 000	40 993	34 852	5 277	40 129	35 960	6 008	41 968	38 829	7 105	45 934
80-84	28 304	1 941	30 245	28 194	2 055	30 249	27 809	2 319	30 128	26 500	2 491	28 991
85-89	14 160	429	14 589	14 133	484	14 617	14 548	588	15 136	14 814	661	15 475
≥ 90	2 944	22	2 966	5 669	50	5 719	6 176	77	6 253	7 350	112	7 462
Total	887 357	583 032	1 470 389	884 021	587 962	1 471 983	878 828	592 009	1 470 837	875 395	597 077	1 472 472

Table S3. List of the 20 antidiabetics with the pictogram “medicines and driving” more consumed in Castile and León into the study period (packages/year).

Code ATC	Name	Antidiabetic Type	Packages/year		
			Men	Women	Total
A10BD07	Metformin and sitagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	107757	73555	181311
A10BD08	Metformin and vildagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	90540	64416	154956
A10AE04	Insuline glargine	Insulin	81440	68007	149446
A10BB09	Glicazide	Oral antidiabetic	46076	41839	87915
A10BX02	Repaglinide	Oral antidiabetic	39302	36674	75976
A10BH01	Sitagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	28064	33067	61131
A10BH05	Linagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	26546	27613	54159
A10BB12	Glimepiride	Oral antidiabetic	24021	20851	44872
A10AD05	Insulin aspart, intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting	Insulin	16333	16731	33064
A10AE05	Insulin detemir	Insulin	16077	16479	32556
A10AB05	Insulin aspart, fast acting	Insulin	17641	13987	31628
A10BK01	Dapagliflozin	Oral antidiabetic	16602	12370	28972
A10BH02	Vildagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	12891	16047	28938
A10BD11	Metformin and linagliptin	Oral antidiabetic	15908	11895	27803
A10BJ02	Liraglutide	Oral antidiabetic	13435	12447	25882
A10AB04	Insulin lispro, fast acting	Insulin	11148	9867	21015
A10AD04	Insulin lispro, intermediate or long acting combined with fast acting	Insulin	99983	10002	20000
A10BJ05	Dulaglutide	Oral antidiabetic	10758	8652	19410
A10BK03	Empagliflozin	Oral antidiabetic	11649	76238	19272
A10BD15	Metformin and dapagliflozin	Oral antidiabetic	9976	6917	16893

Table S4. Consumption of oral antidiabetic without the pictogram “medicines and driving” in Castile and León into the study period (packages/year).

Code ATC	Name	Packages/year		
		Men	Women	Total
A10BA02	Metformin	397527	318359	715886
A10BF01	Acarbose	3983	4091	8073
A10BG03	Pioglitazone	2459	2463	4922
A10BD05	Metfomin and pioglitazone	2601	1690	4291
A10BX01	Guar gum	166	271	437